

Table of Contents

Top 7 Papers selected by the Evaluation Committee

Constraints on upscaling and social inclusion in smart city living lab experiments and ways to anticipate them: lessons from four “smarter” labs by Francesca Cellina, Roberta Castri, Mario Diethart, Thomas Höflechner, Nicola Da Schio, Marc Dijk.....	11
Innovation Management in Living Lab projects: the Innovatrix Framework by Dimitri Schuurman, Aron-Levi Herregodts, Annabel Georges, Olivier Rits.....	26
International Innovation Sprint Bridging the Sustainability Gap between Metropolitan Core and Peripheries by Tuija Hirvikoski, Kaisla Saastamoinen and Mikael Uitto.....	43
Learning with Community: Developing Citizen-Led Housing by Shaofu Huang, Ruth Deakin Crick, Melissa Mean, Carolyn Hassan, Colin Taylor.....	57
Participatory software development via Living Labs: A case of Deajeon by Hee-Sook. Yoo, Su-jin. Jung, Seong-gyu. Park, Miran. Cho.....	77
Transnational piloting for smooth internationalization of health-tech start-ups by Päivi Haho, Metropolia and Virpi Kaartti.....	89
User needs and expectations as a challenging factor for successful living lab research initiatives involving older adults: The DDRI Experience by Tiziana C. Callari, Louise Moody, Nikki Holliday, Ed Russell, Janet Saunders, Gill Ward, Julie Woodley.....	104

Actors motivations, needs and expectations

Living labs as instrument for societal change: the role of intermediary actors and activities by Jos van den Broek, Timo Maas, Isabelle van Elzakker, Jasper Deuten.....	121
Models for Living Lab’s sustainability. Evidences from Italy and the Netherlands Edoardo Gualandi and Luca Leonardi.....	134
Motivational Goals for using Electronic Health Record Applications by Rachel Burrows, Sonja Pedell, Leon Sterling, Tim Miller, Antonette Mendoza.....	151
Smart Campus: a route using 4G and 5G by Esmat Mirzamany and Joe Barrett.....	161
Spectrum Analysis Digital Arts-and-Culture Assets and the Future of Co Creating Decentralised Technologies by Olivier Zephir, Soenke Zehle, Olivier Buchheit.....	173
The Austrian Real-World Laboratories - How to manage multi-stakeholder engagement in the wide field of mobility research by Lina Mosshammer, Doris Wiederwald.....	187
The Developing Process of the Digital Game Which Supports Well-being of	

Small Children by Päivi Marjanen, Janne Pirttikoski, Vesa Valkonen and Viktoria Tiainen..... 200

Governance and process-related areas

“Daegu Living Labs” as City Innovation Platform by Hee Dae Kim 214

Listening to locals? Question-oriented approach in Field Lab Amsterdam East by Sandra Bos 230

Living Labs – an Approach for achieving Sustainable Change in City Logistics by Nina Nesterova, Hans Quak, Tariq van Rooijen 238

Living-Lab-as-a-Service: Exploring the market and sustainability offers of Living Labs in Germany by Justus von Geibler, Julius Piwowar, Annika Greven..... 252

Schools4energy: a living laboratory for energy awareness in schools by Carmelina Cosmi, Filomena Pietrapertosa, Giuliano Sarricchio, Michele Giordano, Monica Proto, Marco Tancredi, Monica Salvia 272

The Circle of Mediators: Towards a governance model for tackling sustainability challenges in a city by Anne Äyväri, Annukka Jyrämä, Tuija Hirvikoski 287

The management of information and knowledge flows in Urban Living Labs: a constructivist approach by Carolina Campalans..... 306

Theoretical and Methodological Challenges

Applying the Living Lab Approach for the Design of Public Spaces– A Living Lab Case Study by Sonja Pedell, Gareth Priday, Alen Keirnan, Flavia Marcello, and Andrew Murphy 320

Comparison of Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Business Models – Preliminary result based on Business Model Canvas Evaluation by Teemu Santonen, Mikko Julin 339

Developing a mutualized R&D for network organizations based on Living Lab methods: the transformation of Sion military airport into a commercial airport by Emmanuel Fragnière, Benjamin Nanchen, Marine Héritier, Randolph Ramseyer, Magali Dubosson and Joelle Mastelic 358

Evaluating the Performance of the Regional Living Lab Concept on Integrated Sustainable Energy Planning by Giannouli Ioanna, Tourkolias Christos, Georgiou Paraskevas, Cantero Celada Sergio, Fernández Maroto Miguel 375

Evolving Community Living Labs through Dual Safety Knowledge Circulation Systems to Prevent Injuries in Children by Mikiko Oono, Yoshifumi Nishida, Koji Kitamura, Kimiko Deguchi 396

Initiating Participation: Methodological and Practical Challenges of Living Lab Projects for Early Stages of Research and Development by Andreas Bischof, Albrecht Kurze, Sören Totzauer, Michael Storz, Kevin Lefeuvre, Arne Berger..... 407

Living Lab 65+ – Participatory testing of technical assistance systems in the natural home environment of senior citizens by Misoch, S., Lehmann, S., Pauli, C., Hämmerle, V., Guggenbühl, U. & Konstantas, D.....	422
Living Lab Research: A State-of-the-Art Review and Steps towards a Research Agenda by Abdolrasoul Habibipour	432
Making open innovation work for Sustainable Development Goals: Sustainability-orientation and assessment based on the SDG-Check by Justus von Geibler, Julius Piwowar, Annika Greven.....	448
Solar Living Lab: implementing sustainable experimentation process, responsible innovation and community engagement in a solar energy research facility by Silvana Di Bono, Filippo Paredes and Fabio Maria Montagnino.....	462
The benefits and challenges of co-creation with seniors: an interdisciplinary social innovation project designed to improve quality of life by D. Campisi, N. Nyffeler, D. Roulet Schwab, V. Le Fort, L. Bergeron	481
The Island Approach (TIA): a suited projective technique for evaluating a bevy of attributes by Natasja Van Buggenhout, Wendy Van den Broeck, Iris Jennes ..	496